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ASSESSMENT OF LIQUEFACTION HAZARDS ON THE BANK OF PADMA RIVER AT AFSARSHEIKHER PARA BY MEANS OF SOILS PARTICLE SIZES AND SPT-N VALUES

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ABSTRACT

River bank failure occurs in different ways at which the coordination of hydraulic and geotechnical means are utmost key aspects. Afsarsheikher Para is one of the vulnerable bank side of the Padma river adjacent to Daulatdia ferry ghat of Goalanda upazilla of Rajbari district. The study findings indicate that the soil strata are very loose to dense in consistency and there is no bonding between the soil particles. Pore pressure increases with the increases of saturation and shear strength decreases with the increases of pore pressure. On the other hand, the standard penetration resistance – N values have been changed along all the boreholes which make the soil layers sometime loose and sometime dense. As a result rising of water level intensifies water pressure and increased velocity contributes the bank failure due to liquefaction. Hence the river bank and the homogeneous soil zone as long will be liquefied due to water pressure and velocity. Under these circumstances geotechnical engineers need to soil strengthening and also sand drain measures may be practices mainly to increase the rate of drainage seepage way. It is also recommended to investigate the soil properties and make their design accordingly for river training and bank protection works.

Keywords: Padma river bank, Liquefaction hazards, Soil Particles, SPT-N values

1. INTRODUCTION

The different amounts of sand, silt and clay exists in the soils in different parts of Bangladesh as the rivers deposit different amounts of these particles in different parts of flood plains when they overflow the land. Sandy material is deposited near the river banks and silty material further away from the banks whereas clay in the low areas furthest away from the river. When rivers change their courses, the pattern of sandy and silty materials are seen on the slightly higher ridges of the rivers and clay materials are seen left behind of the adjoining basins (Brammer, 1996).

The riverbank failure is a common problem in Bangladesh. There are many types of failure occurred at river bank. It is utmost important to identify the appropriate type of failure mechanism of the river bank as it is necessary for design of the river bank protection. It is often seen at monsoon that the river is full of pressure with high stream velocity. During this period the river bank fails up to vast area and sometimes the previous bank line could not recognized as the massive area is converted into fluid. I.e., apparently it is seen that the area is occupied by water and water what we call it liquefaction (Liquefaction, <https://depts.washington.edu/liquefy/html/where/where1.html>).

1.1 Soil Liquefaction

Soil liquefaction occurs when a saturated or partially saturated soil substantially loses strength and stiffness in response to an applied stress such as shaking during an earthquake or other sudden change in stress condition, in which a solid behaves like a liquid.

Allen Hazen (1918) first used the term “liquefied” during the failure of the Calaveras Dam in California. He described that if the pressure of the water in the pores is great enough to carry the entire load, it will have the effect of holding the particles apart and of producing a condition that is practically equivalent to that of quicksand. As a result, the initial movement of some part of the material accumulates pressure first on one point and then on another successively as the early points of concentration was liquefied (Soil Liquefaction,Wikipedia).

1.2 Occurrence

Liquefaction occurs more in loose to moderately saturate granular soils such as silty sands or sands and gravels containing impermeable sediments with poor drainage. During wave loading, loose sands tend to decrease in volume, which produces an increase in their pore water pressures and consequently a decrease in shear strength resulting the reduction in effective stress.

Sands and silts of similar grain size deposits most susceptible to liquefaction are young (Holocene-age, deposited within the last 10,000 years) (well-sorted), in beds at least meters thick, and saturated with water. Such deposits are often found along stream beds, beaches, dunes, and areas where windblown silt (loess) and sand have accumulated. Examples of soil liquefaction include quicksand, quick clay, turbidity currents and earthquake-induced liquefaction.

Depending on the initial void ratio, the soil material can respond to loading either strain-softening or strain-hardening. Strain-softened soils, e.g. loose sands, can be triggered to collapse, either monotonically or cyclically, if the static shear stress is greater than the ultimate or steady-state shear strength of the soil. In this case flow liquefaction occurs, where the soil deforms at a low constant residual shear stress. If stress reversal occurs, the effective shear stress could reach zero.

The resistance of the cohesionless soil to liquefaction will depend on the density of the soil, confining stresses, soil structure (fabric, age and cementation), the magnitude and duration of the cyclic loading, and the extent to which shear stress reversal occurs (Liquefaction, <https://depts.washington.edu/liquefy/html/where/where1.html>).

1.3 Impact of Liquefaction on Different Soil Groups

Arora (2010) classified the soil in major divisions and groups which is shown below:

	Major Division		Group Symbols	Typical Names	
Coarse-Grained Soils [More than 50% retained on No. 200 sieve (0.075 mm)]	Sand [more than 50% of coarse fraction passing No.4 sieve (4.75 mm)]	Clean Sands	SW	Well graded sands	
			SP	Poorly graded sands	
		Sands with fines		SM	Silty sands
				SC	Clayey sands
Fine grained soils [50% or more passing No. 200 sieve (0.075 mm)]	Silts and clays Liquid Limit 50% or less		ML	Inorganic silts of low plasticity	
			CL	Inorganic clays of low to medium plasticity	
			OL	Organic silts of low plasticity	

Liquefaction occurs when all the five conditions must be satisfied such as i) The soil is cohesionless, ii) The soil is loose, iii) The soil is saturated, iv) There is a shaking of ground of the required intensity and duration, and v) The undrained conditions develop in the soil due to its limited permeability.

Liquefaction can also occur in the soil deposit at any depth where these conditions are satisfied. He observed that liquefaction normally occurs in the soil classified as SP in Indian Standard Classifications when the SPT number N is less than 15. However, sometimes liquefaction may also occur in the soil classified as SW, SM, and ML (Source: Arora, 2010).

Bank failure is a common issue at Goalanda upazilla in Rajbari of Bangladesh. Afsarsheikher Para is more vulnerable bank failure prone area and affects all aspects such as lives, cultivation, vegetation, farming including numerous socio-economic problems. Bank failure occurs in many rivers in many mechanisms. Liquefaction is one of the most catastrophic bank failure mechanisms among them. Since few years, some of the meter and kilometre areas are being soared into the river and this situation has been worsen among the couple of years. People are being suffered unbearable miseries out of tolerance in lost their house and occupation and migrated to another place resulting in socio-economic crisis. It is crying needs sustainable river bank protection for the people of this area. In this context it is needed to find out the appropriate reasons and easy way out for protect the river bank for a design engineer. Here it is a tiny attempt to assist the implementing authority of the river bank protection works. Under such circumstances, it has been attempted to undertake the study and disseminate its result through a paper.

Under such circumstances, an attempt has been made to identify the type of river bank failure mechanism and assessment of liquefaction hazards at Afsarsheikher Para of the Goalanda upazilla of Padma river by means of soils particle sizes and their SPT-values as Afsarsheikher Para is one of the liquefaction prone areas which were apparently predicted.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Sampling And In-Situ Testing Location

The data have been collected from the investigation report of Daulatdia and Paturia side of Padma river of Bangladesh wherever Afsarsheikher Para was the location of Daulatdia side has been considered for this study which have been shown in Figure 1, 2 and 3 respectively. In this study both the in-situ testing data and laboratory testing data have been used. The location of the study area is 1km up of Daulatdia ferry ghat of Goalanda upazilla of Rajbari district of Bangladesh. The coordinate of Borehole No. 1 of the location is Northing-2631766 and Easting -783429, Borehole No. 2 of the location is Northing-2631715 and Easting-782452 & Borehole No.3 of the location is Northing-2631566 and Easting-782475.

Figure 1: Study Area at Afsarsheikher Para, Rajbari

Figure 2: Boring hole Sketch (Not to Scale)

2.2 Boring Hole of Sampling And Field Investigation

The boring points have been allocated in accordance with following sketch (not to scale). The boring distances are from the bank line to the hole of the study has been shown in Figure 2.

The samples (disturbed and undisturbed) have been collected from the selected coordinates of the study area by wash boring method and the SPT values have been recorded for blows on spoon per 6 inch penetration of every disturbed samples collection (Source: Geotechnical Research Report, 2020).

As river bank is exclusively associated with soils grain sizes and their properties as well as water level. So, water level and ground water level are identical for bank failure reasons. In this context, water level and ground water level are considered for this study. These data have been collected from BWDB and WARPO of Bangladesh and used them at contemporary period of field investigation.

2.3 Laboratory Investigation

Saturation, pore pressure and shear strength are the most important parameters for evaluating the river bank failure incident. Although many other soil testing parameters are interrelated for river bank failure. Grain size of soils is mostly related among all the important parameters such as permeability as well as saturation which give direction of the natural moisture content. In the laboratory, the selected soil parameters which govern the river bank failure are tested. In which natural moisture content, specific gravity, permeability, shear strength and grain sizes are utmost important and tested directly. Saturation is determined using equation $S = wG/e$ where, S =Saturation, w =moisture content and G =specific Gravity and e = void ratio at which some void ratio is calculated from consolidation of direct shear test and others are found relevant to their particles sizes and density (Garg, 2010). Pore pressures $u = h\gamma_w$ are determined from consideration of soil strata with their respective field depth and ground water level. Shear strength is determined from the data of direct shear test using equation, $S = c + \sigma \tan \phi$ where, S =shear strength, c = cohesion, σ = effective stress and ϕ = angle of internal friction. Grain size has been analysed according to ASTM-D421-58 and D422-63(Bowles, 1978) and the grain sizes have been accounted from the graph followed in Unified Soil Classification System.

Soil Classification range and important characteristics of soils for embankments and foundations are shown in Table 1, 2 and 3 respectively.

Table 1: Sand, Silt and Clay according to their range

Name of the grain	Range of Values in mm
Gravel	<76.2-4.76>
Sand	<4.76-0.074>
Silt	<0.074-0.002>
Clay	<0.002

(Source: Garg, 2010)

Table 2: Soil Characteristics pertinent to embankments and foundations

Soil Group	Value for embankment	Permeability cm/sec	Compaction Characteristics	Dry density, gm/cm ³	Value for foundation	Requirements for seepage control
SM (Silty sands, poorly graded sand-silt mixtures)	Fairly stable, not particularly suited to shells, may be used for impervious cores or dikes	$K=10^{-3}$ to 10^{-6}	Good with close control; Rubber tyred or Sheeps foot Roller	1.76-2.00	Good to poor bearing value depending on density	Upstream blanket and toe drainage or wells

(Source: Garg, 2010)

Table 3: Density Index (I_D) of Sand

Number of blows (SPT-N values)	Density Index (I_D)
0-4	Very loose
4-10	Loose
10-30	Medium Dense
30-50	Dense
Over 50	Very dense

(Source: Terzaghi & Peck, 1948)

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Typical soil strata of all the three bore holes have been shown in the Figure 3 and data of field investigation and laboratory investigation have been presented in the tabular form in Table 1 and 2 respectively.

Sample ID	Depth (m)	SPT (N-values)
D-1	1.5	CLAY, little fine sand
UD-1	2.5	FINE SAND, little silt, trace mica
D-2	3.0	FINE SAND, little silt, trace mica
D-3	4.5	FINE SAND, little silt, trace mica
UD-2	5.0	FINE SAND, little silt, trace mica
D-4	6.0	FINE SAND, some silt, trace mica
D-5	7.5	FINE SAND, little silt, trace mica
D-6	9.0	FINE SAND, little silt, trace mica
D-7	10.5	FINE SAND, little silt, trace mica
D-8	12.0	FINE SAND, little silt, trace mica
D-9	13.5	FINE SAND, little silt, trace mica
D-10	15.0	FINE SAND, little silt, trace mica
D-11	16.5	FINE SAND, some silt, trace mica
D-12	18.0	FINE SAND, little silt, trace mica
D-13	19.5	FINE SAND, little silt, trace mica
D-14	21.0	FINE SAND, little silt, trace mica

Figure 3: Soil strata of AfsarSheiker Para, Daulatdia, Rajbar

Figure 4: Schematic Soil strata of AfsarSheiker Para, Daulatdia, Rajbari

Test results of different parameters for cohesive and non-cohesive soils are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Table showing the properties of cohesive and non-cohesive soils up to the depth 1.5 m and after the depth of 1.5m of Afsarsheikher Para of Daulatdia

For cohesive soils up to the depth 1.5 m											
Depth in m	Name of the para-meter	Colour	Natural Moisture Content (N.M.C) in %	*SPT-N value	Sand in (%)	Silt in (%)	Clay in (%)	Plasticity Index in (%)	Permeability, k in mm/sec	Saturation in (%)	Pore pressure in kN/m ²
1.5	Range of Values	Grey	24.24 - 34.63	3-7	5-16	66-84	10-18	9-17	7.15 x10 ⁻⁵	87-95	0-164
For non-cohesive soils after the depth 1.5 m											

Depth in m	Name of the parameter	Colour	N.M.C in %	*SPT-N value	Specific Gravity, G _s	Sand in (%)	Silt in (%)	Clay in (%)	Cohesion, c in kN/m ²	Angle of internal friction, Ø in degree	Permeability, k in mm/sec	Saturation in (%)	Pore pressure in kN/m ²
1.5-22	Range of Values	Grey	6.87-33.95	5-50	2.646-2.70	23-97	3-77	0-1	0-2	19-24	2.28x10 ⁻³ - 8.07x10 ⁻²	87-95	0-164

*SPT-Standard Penetration Resistance for N- value

From Table 4 it has been observed that cohesive soil layer is up to the depth of about (0-1.5) m and the layers after that are non-cohesive up to the depth of exploration. The SPT values are (3-7) for cohesive soils where the SPT values are (5-50) for non-cohesive soils. The consistency of cohesive soils varies from soft to medium stiff and the plasticity is medium. The clay particle varies from (9-18)%, silt particle varies from (66-84)% and sand particle varies from (4-16)% for cohesive soils. Whatever it is, the soil layers are dominating at the site through its non-cohesive characters. The density index of non-cohesive soils varies from loose to dense and the plasticity is non-plastic. The cohesion varies from (0-2) kN/m² and the angle of internal friction varies from (19-24) degree. The permeability varies from (2.28x10⁻³-8.07x10⁻²) mm/sec. The specific gravity varies from (2.663-2.721). The parameters have been stated altogether indicate the soils classification and its strength and seepage situation.

3.1 Ground Water Level And Surface Water Level At Daulatdia Side

Figure 5: Graph showing the variation of Ground Water Level from July’17 To July’18 at Daulatdia side of Padma River (Source:BWDB)

Figure 6: Surface water level (SWL) of Goalandaghat and ground waterlevel (GWL)of 3 stations of Goalandaghat, Rajbari with time. (Source: BWDB as well as Geotechnical Research Report, 2020)

3.2 Variation of Ground Water Level with Surface Water Level at Daulatdia Side

Ground water level and surface water level at the study area for the period of January’2018 to April’2019 is analyzed and shown in Figure-6. In Figure-6 the variation of ground water table of three stations of Goalanda of Rajbari and the surface water level of Goalanda of Daulatdia side of Rajbari on January’2018 to April’2019 have been shown in the graph. In the graph it has been found that ground water level changes with the change in surface water level. In the month of March surface water level is lower where it has been gradually increased after then. The increasing trend of water level is up to the month of September’18. The water level has been decreased rapidly up to the month of December’18. On the other hand, the ground water level decreases up to April’18 and gradually increases up to the month June’18 and then rapidly increases up to the mid of September,18 and then decreased gradually up to the month March’19.

3.3 Variation of SPT- N values with Depth and Particle sizes at Afsarsheikher Para of Daulatdia side of Padma River

Figure 7: A comparison graph of three holes showing the Standard Penetration Resistance-N(SPT) value with the corresponding depth at Afsarsheikher Para site of Daulatdia side of Padma river

Figure 8: A comparison graph of three holes showing the Natural Moisture Content(N.M.C) value with the corresponding depth at Afsarsheikher Para site of Daulatdia side of Padma river

Figure-7 represents the variation of SPT-N values with depth in hole no.1 –no.3 of Afsarsheikher Para site. From the graph it is found that SPT values increases with depth in all the holes however, SPT fluctuates several times in all the holes as investigation states. After analyzing the bore holes of Afsarsheikher Para at Daulatdia side, it is determined that these SPT variation has been followed the natural moisture content, density, particle size, age of deposition and other geotechnical properties.

From figure-7, it is also observed that the SPT values are varying from loose to medium dense up to the depth 9m in terms density index at all the holes of non-cohesive soils however, the SPT values are loose in hole no.1 in the maximum depth with few exceptions and there is no plastic layer rather than 1.5m. The hole no.1 is very near to bank line which is hit first by the water pressure during raising of water level.

In terms of natural moisture content consideration from Figure-8 it has been observed that the natural moisture content is high up to the depth 9m whereas it has been gradually decreased with the increases of depth. The natural moisture content gives direction that loose soil contains more water than dense soil.

From figure-9 it has been found at three holes that the particle sizes such as clay particle varies from (0-1)% rather than 1.5m, silt particle varies from(3-76)% and sand particle varies from (23-97)%. Considering the particle sizes of the soils it has been found that soils are uniform graded poor soils.

Figure 9: A comparison graph of three holes showing the Percentage of Grain with the corresponding depth at Afsarsheikher Para site of Daulatdia side of Padma river

3.4 Effect of Saturation on Pore Pressure and Shear Strength

Saturation is determined using equation $S = wG/e$ where, S =Saturation, w =moisture content and G =specific Gravity at which some void ratio is calculated from consolidation of direct shear test and others are found relevant to their particles sizes and density(Garg, 2010). Pore pressures $u = h\gamma_w$ are determined from consideration of soil strata with their respective field depth and ground water level. Shear strength is determined from the data of direct shear test using equation, $S = c + \sigma \tan \phi$ where, S =shear strength, c = cohesion, σ = effective stress and ϕ = angle of internal friction.

Figure 10: Graph showing the effect of saturation on pore pressure at Afsarsheikher Para of Daulatdia side of Padma river

Figure 11: Graph showing the effect of pore pressure on shear strength at Afsarsheikher Para of Daulatdia side of Padma river

In Figure-10, the pore water pressure has been plotted with its respective saturation. The data have been considered here on the month of February'18. From figure it is observed that the pore water pressure has been increased with the increases of saturation. Their corresponding pore water pressures have been increased from 0 to 164kN/m² accordingly. However, the saturation at hole no.-1 of Afsarsheikher Para site is slightly different in comparison with other two holes. Here one reason is the hole-No.1 is very adjacent to bank line and another reasons are soil layers and its properties. As a result of rising water level, saturation has been increased as well as pore pressure.

In Figure-11, shear strength has been plotted with corresponding pore pressure. From the graph it is observed that shear strength decreases with the increases of pore water pressure in both the holes. Shear strength of the soils of hole no.-1 and hole no-3 are less than that of hole no.-2. The shear strength of the hole no.-2 has been varied rapidly with pore pressure. The variation of particle sizes of the soil effects the pore pressure as well as shear strength. The ground level was not existed at the alike coordinate and ground water level as well as water level. That's why the soil strength is not homogeneous however, the location was identical.

3.5 Effect of Surface Water Level on River Bank Soil

The elevation of bore hole is 7mPWD (0 m) wherever the low water level is 3mPWD and high water level is 8mPWD. From the low water level and above, the soil layer contains uniform graded poor soil layers make non-cohesive soils layer. The soil strata are very loose to dense in condition and there is no bonding between the soil particles as CLAY particles are absent. Particularly from 6mPWD to 1mPWD, the soil layers are loose. These soil layers meet the intensive water pressure and velocity. From Figure-10 & 11 it has been observed that pore pressure increases with the increases of saturation and shear strength decreases with the increases of pore pressure. Accordingly, due to rise of water level the pore pressure will increase with the increases of saturation and shear strength will decrease. The shear strength tends to zero resulting the soil lose its strength.

4. CONCLUSION

It is found that the elevation of bore hole is 7mPWD (0 m) wherever the low water level is 3mPWD and high water level is 8mPWD. From the low water level and above, the soil layer contains uniform graded poor soil layers make non-cohesive soils layer. The soil strata are very loose to dense in condition and there is no bonding between the soil particles as CLAY particles are absent. Particularly from 6mPWD to 1mPWD, the soil layers are loose. These soil layers meet the intensive water pressure and velocity.

From the saturation, pore pressure and shear strength results it have been observed that pore pressure increases with the increases of saturation and shear strength decreases with the increases of pore pressure. Accordingly, due to rise of water level the pore pressure will increase with the increases of saturation and shear strength will decrease. The shear strength tends to zero resulting the soil lose its strength. On the other hand, the standard penetration resistance-N values have been changed along all the holes as bored which make the soil layers sometime loose and sometime medium dense to dense. As a result the river bank tends toward the failure disposition. Subsequently rising water level intensify water pressure resultant the bank failure at Afsarsheikher Para. As liquefaction occurs at loose undrained non-cohesive soils whose SPT-N values are within 15 causes intensive water pressure and velocity. Thus, Afsarsheikher Para and the layers as the soil character is identical are affected by liquefaction. Hence the river bank as well as the homogeneous soil zone as long liquefies due to water pressure and velocity.

5. RECOMMENDATION

The study area is at the river bank and the soil strata are very loose to dense in condition. At monsoon, the soil is submerged and become full of saturation indeed. In that condition, the increasing trend of pore pressure decreases the soil strength. As a result the river bank tends toward the failure disposition. Under such situation, water pressure intensify resulting hit the bank and liquefy the river bank as long the soil profile is identical. So, an engineer needs to required soil strengthening opportunities in this regard. Sand drain may practice mainly to increase the rate of drainage in the embankment as the horizontal drainage occurs due to because of sand drains. Consequently, the sand drain may accelerate the process of dissipation of excess pore water created by surcharge. The geotechnical engineers must the design of foundation of the river bank protection structures after investigation of the soil, its characteristics and its extent.

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